

Bioeconomy in countries of the Mekong region: Stakeholder understanding and perceptions in Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Bioeconomy
Sustainable management
South East Asia
Forestry
Strategy
Sustainable development goals

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyse, evaluate, and compare the status of the bioeconomy concept in the Mekong region in three countries, namely Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. The research questions focused on the perception of the bioeconomy concept by the governments and industries, the barriers to its development, and the prerequisites for its development in the region, and also explored whether it is reflected in the related existing official strategic documents. The study used a combined methodology that included qualitative document analysis and an online questionnaire distributed to public and private sector representatives in all three countries, analysed through Advocacy Coalition Framework theory lenses. The results showed that while the bioeconomy is acknowledged in many institutions of the South-East Asian countries and closely connected to the sustainable development and circular economy, there is a lack of a clear bioeconomy vision, resulting in the absence of dedicated bioeconomy strategies in these countries. The results indicated that the bioeconomy concept is a new emerging concept in these countries, which was perceived as the most important barrier to its development. Unfortunately, there is limited expert knowledge of the bioeconomy, and insufficient support from the state-level, followed by low technological development. The study also highlighted the irreplaceable role of the forest-based sector in the bioeconomy concept. The authors suggest further research on the economic valuation of the bioeconomy to promote its adoption, as well as a greater involvement of key policymakers in the individual countries for its further development, specifically in Thailand and Vietnam, or a further comparison with selected European countries. The study also suggests several possible assumptions for the development of the bioeconomy in the studied countries, based on their different levels of technological development and industrialization.

1. Introduction

1.1. Bioeconomy as a global concept

A common vision of sustainable development around the world was adopted into 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the United Nations (UN), which include economic, social, and ecological development (IACGB. International Advisory Council on Global Bioeconomy,

2020; Thrän and Moesenfechtel, 2020; Biber-Freudenberger et al., 2020). In this transition, the bioeconomy is a crucial concept comprising an economy based on biological resources from the land and sea, such as crops, forests, animals, and microorganisms, to produce food, materials, and energy (EU, 2018). Due to its broader view, the bioeconomy is a continuously evolving concept rather than a static idea (IACGB. International Advisory Council on Global Bioeconomy, 2020; Refsgaard et al., 2021). The concept provides numerous technological

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103190>

Received 14 April 2023; Received in revised form 22 February 2024; Accepted 27 February 2024

Available online 13 March 2024

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opportunities to enhance the economic growth and social progress while reducing greenhouse emissions and resource use (IACGB. *International Advisory Council on Global Bioeconomy*, 2020; Fielding and Aung, 2018). The two main bioeconomy views are biotechnology innovations and resource substitution perspectives. In the former perspective, the growth of high-technology industries presumes investment in innovation and human resources (Lewandowski, 2018). Though the resource substitution perspective remains essential, many authors, e.g., Lovrić et al. (2020); Bröring and Vanacker (2022) emphasise the biotechnology innovation perspective due to its greater potential to adapt to and mitigate the effects of climate change and improve the state of global ecosystems.

The societal transformation into a bioeconomy is characterised by the “supply side”. It is based on biological and biotechnological processes to supply goods and services (Lewandowski, 2018). According to Ronzon et al. (2022), bioeconomy activities target ecosystem and biomass-using services. As a result, the authors have identified four types of bioeconomy services: (i) those associated with tangible bio-based goods, (ii) natural environment-related services, (iii) knowledge-based services, and (iv) support services for the development of bio-based markets. All these services are related to agriculture, forestry, fishing, the printing industry, and industries connected to producing food, beverages, wood products, and paper. Due to the variety of the services provided, the bioeconomy requires a holistic and transdisciplinary view, highly collaborative interaction and cooperation between governments, science, businesses, society, and requires a change in consumer behaviour (EU, 2018).

Several countries have developed bioeconomy strategies and national-level policy documents in the past two decades based on relevant priorities, resources, and conditions (Bracco and Flammini, 2018; Lewandowski, 2018). Globally, not all policy documents use the term “bioeconomy”. Three diverse concepts are interconnected in their shared goal of sustainability, mainly appearing in geographical regions. They are (i) the circular economy, which dominates in China, (ii) the bioeconomy, predominant in Europe, and (iii) the green economy, which can be found globally (Székács, 2017; D’Amato et al., 2017). A bioeconomy transition provides additional reasons for countries to share the benefits and burdens of the transformation process (Stark et al., 2022). For instance, the EU made one of the most robust bioeconomy implementations, which promotes consistency between policies and incorporates it so that it mainly focuses on research and development, engaging multiple groups, and enhancing competitiveness (EU, 2012; Scordato et al., 2017).

In contrast, the United States of America (US) has a narrow bioeconomy approach that potentially offers a better track of innovations and dynamics with mature sectors of the economy, like agriculture, forestry, and the food industry, with their respective emerging activities. According to Frisvold et al. (2021), converging the US and European (EU) approaches facilitates collaboration and policy integration. In Latin America and the Caribbean, the bioeconomy is built on four pillars – sustainability, promotion of climate action, promotion of social action and innovations (Rodríguez et al., 2019). In other countries like India, and many African nations, the use of the term “bioeconomy” is increasing because they focus on the expansion of the use of natural resources and apply the bioeconomy transition through fossil fuel substitution or resource renewability. However, as Bastos Lima (2022) and Ncube et al. (2022) note, the sustainability of bio-based production is not pronounced in the discourse on the topic. Hence, these countries need to prioritise policies that reinforce the care for the environment and local communities in fair and empowering terms during the transition (Bergamo et al., 2022). Moreover, Halonen et al. (2022), and Johnson and Altman (2014) state that biomass providers in rural areas benefit urban centres, which shows the importance of local solutions, the involvement, and actors such as community leaders, rural entrepreneurs or economic developers who will allow further bioeconomy growth if their goals are appropriately aligned. This case is well-

represented in the Mekong region, characterised by its large rural population, diverse culture, ecosystems, and political systems (Onraphai et al., 2021).

A forest bioeconomy can be defined only as the utilisation of the forest biomass (e.g., Hetemäki, 2017; Ronzon et al., 2020). In a broader meaning, a forest bioeconomy can include the utilisation of wood and non-wood production from the forest including ecosystem services and innovative approaches. According to Lovrić et al. (2020), a forest-based bioeconomy includes forest systems, the forest biomass and raw materials, primary processing like pulp, bioenergy and wood-processing, and also secondary processing like biorefineries and biopolymers. The forest-based bioeconomy is especially dominant in forest-rich countries (Karvonen et al., 2017), the importance of forestry in the bioeconomy is emphasised by several authors, e.g., Böcher et al., 2020; Jonsson et al., 2021; Hetemäki and Kangas, 2022; Park and Grundmann, 2023. According to Siegel et al. (2022), South American countries emphasise the key issues connected to a forest bioeconomy, i.e., biodiversity, ecosystem services, biomass and bioenergy.

1.2. Bioeconomy in the Mekong region

Any consideration of the bioeconomy concept is based on the natural and economic conditions of the entire region. The main production and exports in the region are based on livestock, plants, trees, and crops, all important components of food, bio-based products, and energy resources, which need economic sustainability (Masud et al., 2018). Their rapid economic growth has brought different types of environmental and economic challenges related to the population increase, waste generation, changes in urbanisation, and a decrease in fossil fuels for climate protection (WBGU, 2011). Moreover, most Mekong countries are based on an unsustainable growth model and natural resource exploitation, while being prone to natural disasters due to climate change, making their situation more difficult (São, 2019). For these reasons, it is important to encourage governments, industry, and society in the region to substantially invest into a sustainable bioeconomy, while providing a base for equality, enabling the just development of the primary sector (São, 2019; Wang et al., 2022; Lakra and Krishnani, 2022).

Scientific publications devoted to the bioeconomy in Asia have emerged (e.g., Morland and Schier, 2020; Guerrero and Hansen, 2021), however, it is still clear, even according to Gould et al. (2023), that the scope for bioeconomy research in Asia is significant. There are already scientific publications that describe the situation of the bioeconomy and consider its role in the larger states of Asia like China and India in relative detail (e.g., Gould et al., 2023; Duan et al., 2020; Venkata et al., 2018). This topic is often mentioned in connection with the use of biomass (e.g., Mikkilä et al., 2021; Antar et al., 2021). A large number of publications devoted to the bioeconomy do not exist in the countries we studied. Johnson et al. (2022) based on dialogues with stakeholders, tried to identify and analyse the relationship between bioeconomy visions and pathways and their governance. Their study included Thailand, but not any other Asian country.

The first South-East Asian country that launched a National Bioeconomy Programme was Malaysia in 2010, with the National Biotechnology Policy being initiated in 2005 already (Arujanan and Singaram, 2018). The first bio-related strategy in Thailand was the National biotechnology policy framework for 2004 to 2011 (Saardchom, 2017). In 2017, Thailand developed a roadmap focused on high-value products from existing crops, starting with sugar cane and the cassava (Hoogzaad, 2017). It also includes a short to medium and a long-term plan, which includes agriculture and biotechnology, food, biofuels and biochemical industries. The government made substantial efforts to develop a bioeconomy strategy and private firms are set towards innovation in technology, research, and implementation of the bioeconomy through tax incentives (Ngammuangtueng et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2022). The most-relevant strategy connected to the bioeconomy in

Thailand is the Bio-circular-green economy (BCG) model (NSTDA, 2023).

In Lao People's Democratic Republic (Laos), forests represent an important revenue source, contributing 6% of its gross domestic product (GDP). However, forest management during these years presents major challenges (São, 2019). Other than forestry, Laos has great resources regarding hydropower, solid agriculture and a high potential to expand ecotourism (São, 2019). Nevertheless, compared to its neighbouring countries, adopting a bioeconomy strategy is a very slow process. Moreover, because the country is in the heart of the Mekong region, its economy has a strong association with the surrounding countries, and it also involves consumers and producers from other continents (FAO, 2010). That is why the shift to a more sustainable future, in which Laos can safeguard its natural uniqueness and cultural richness is vital (OECD, 2022).

In Vietnam, the country leads the regional fish export market with tilapia, pangasius, and shrimp, followed by other commodities, such as rice, coffee, and wood products (ISPONRE, Viet Nam and SWITCH Asia RPAC, 2022). In connection to forestry, Vietnam is the fifth largest exporter of wood and forest products globally and the largest in the Mekong region. Despite this, Vietnam is facing major problems in manufacturing and with the quality of the plantation timber (VNU-HUS, 2022). Currently, the government of Vietnam is working to realize its potential and accelerate the implementation of plans and strategies to achieve economic growth, while maintaining environmental sustainability. Specifically, regarding the legal corridor, the government also issued and approved national strategies on green growth and sustainable development (Government of Vietnam - Prime Minister of, 2012; Government of Vietnam – Prime Minister of Vietnam, 2021). On the other hand, the legal system is still not really synchronous — there is no specific legal document regulating green energy, renewable energy and the bioeconomy strategy, and the country counts on regulations applicable to the agriculture, forestry, and land use change sectors. Nonetheless, the responsible actors are working on more substantial actions, moving towards a more sustainable economic system.

Since forest-based sectors are one of the pillars of the bioeconomy, forest-rich countries like Thailand, Vietnam and Laos, have certain expectations from the forest bioeconomy and the related businesses (Halonen et al., 2022) without sacrificing the well-stocked forests and biodiversity (Halonen et al., 2022) if managed wisely. Forests are crucial to the bioeconomy, providing bio-based materials and products for construction, packaging, textiles, furniture, chemical industries, as well as non-wood forest products that can be used in traditional or new business models (Kallio et al., 2020; Halonen et al., 2022). Thus, the forest bioeconomy is expected to provide a basis for the economic and ecological integrity in the Mekong region. The surplus of bioresources in the Mekong region leaves space for the great potential in the development of bioproducts and services enabling a new take on skills, jobs and economic opportunities (Refsgaard et al., 2021; Onpraphai et al., 2021).

Therefore, in the big picture, the bioeconomy will lead the way to a more resilient society, but it requires teamwork from all the countries to keep the economy, nature, and society developing alongside each other (Bengtsson and Schröder, 2021). It is important to mention that the bioeconomy is not used only as a term, but also presented in its broader context, e.g., in the Bio-Circular-Green Economy initiative (Onpraphai et al., 2021). Consequently, it is essential to acknowledge the actual state and how this bioeconomy transition is perceived in the Mekong region, knowing its potential for developing partnerships to address sustainability issues and improve the actual and future situations.

Since there is no known view of the perception of the bioeconomy in the countries of the Mekong region, this study aims to bring one of the first views of the relevant stakeholders on this concept in their country. By adopting the Advocacy Coalition Framework as a guiding framework, our study provides a robust and structured analysis of the bioeconomy in the Mekong region, offering valuable insights into its perception, adoption, and potential for growth among key stakeholders in Thailand,

Vietnam, and Laos (Sabatier, 1988). These groups' visions included the government and industries' perception, and which sectors are mainly included in the bioeconomy concept. The next goal of this study is to also analyse, evaluate and compare the status of the bioeconomy concept in the countries of the Mekong region: Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos.

For framing the research questions, the Multiple Streams Framework (MSF) theory was considered. MSF (Kingdon, 2010), is an approach for analyzing policymaking across a variety of policies and countries and argues that the policy environment is becoming more amenable to the use of the MSF over time, with complexity and "a post-policy" world becoming more ingrained in governmental decision-making. The theory rejects the rational actor approach and argues that many different solutions exist to any policy issue by assuming the MSF is that ambiguity in problem definition prevents rationality from being useful (Hoefler, 2022). By using the MSF, we tried to examine how bioeconomy concepts move through the problem, policy, and politics streams, and understand the factors that contribute to their uptake or hinder their advancement, because this framework provided us with a systematic way to analyse the dynamics of policy change and the role of various actors, ideas, and events in shaping the bioeconomy agenda in the Mekong region.

The following research questions (RQ) were set:

RQ1: Is the current perceived state of the bioeconomy in the surveyed states reflected in their respective strategic documents?

RQ2: What is the perception of the bioeconomy concepts in the surveyed states?

RQ3: What are the main barriers to the bioeconomy concept in the surveyed states?

RQ4: What are the prerequisites for the development of the bioeconomy in the Mekong region?

At the beginning of our research, we established the following assumptions:

- The stakeholders acknowledge the bioeconomy in the South-East Asian countries.
- The stakeholders across the three selected countries have a common understanding of the bioeconomy as a concept.
- The actor groups in the observed countries identify that the bioeconomy is supported by their governments.
- The barriers and opportunities of the bioeconomy transitions are common across the observed countries.

2. Methods

The methodological approach consisted from closely-connected steps – a literature search, a qualitative document analysis, and an online questionnaire.

2.1. Qualitative document analysis

To get a relevant overview on the implementation of bioeconomy principles in Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos, a document analysis was conducted by the authors of the article. First, the existence of official national-level strategies was reviewed. Then, the documents related to bioeconomy were identified in the surveyed states. The research focused on publicly available books, conference proceedings, student theses, scientific publications in local-language journals, national-level strategies, local-level strategies, laws, regulations, etc. The selection of suitable documents was made with respect to the principles of systematic sampling (Krippendorf, 2019). The analysed documents represented documents related to the bioeconomy and its principles and were sourced from official government publications, domestic and international journals, etc. Considering that we worked with different sources of information and not all of them explicitly mentioned the field of bioeconomy, a qualitative content analysis was used which identifies and searches latent concepts and topics related to the bioeconomy (Tight, 2017; Mayring, 2014). For the document where bioeconomy

characteristics occurred, we noted the explicit phrase and searched for an implicit expression including the presentation of the main idea (similar to Lovrić et al., 2021 and Kleinschmit et al., 2016).

All the assessed documents were analysed in the domestic languages (Thai, Vietnamese, Lao) by native speakers or in English, if available. The essence of the analysis was the search for keywords, that were carefully selected after a joint brainstorming session of the authors. Keywords were used in English or in language modifications and had to have a direct connection to the bioeconomy: “bioeconomy”, “circular economy”, “green economy”, “low-carbon economy”, “renewable materials”, “waste”, “saving”, “development”, “sustainability”, “forestry”, “agriculture”, “wood”, etc., supplemented by others based on the priorities of bioeconomy-related topics in each country. If the keywords occurred in a document, the text was subjected to a detailed assessment to verify the exact phrase meaning. In total, 55 (Thailand 15, Vietnam 29, Laos 11) documents related to the bioeconomy were mapped and assessed. The result of this analysis is presented in the Results section and the researched documents are listed in Appendix 1.

2.2. Questionnaire

In line with the Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF) and drawing upon insights from the literature review and contextual considerations, we formulated an online questionnaire to probe into the perceptions of the bioeconomy within the unique national conditions of Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. This questionnaire design, inspired by the works of Grønmo (2020) and Nordin (2017), incorporated a blend of closed and semi-open multiple-choice questions to elicit respondent perspectives, with each question offering a single-choice response option. Furthermore, within the semi-open questions, an avenue was provided for respondents to articulate qualitative reasoning, fostering a nuanced understanding of their viewpoints. To enhance the granularity of bioeconomy perception, certain questions were constructed employing a six-point Likert scale, as advocated by Yamashita (2022). The questionnaire was initially crafted in English and subsequently translated into the respective national languages of Thai, Vietnamese, and Lao, ensuring accessibility and comfort for respondents to engage in their preferred languages. The questionnaire, encompassing a total of 26 questions across three distinct categories (general inquiries, bioeconomy-focused queries, and forest bioeconomy-specific inquiries), is detailed in Appendix 2.

The administration of this questionnaire was facilitated through the paid version of the Typeform online survey platform, version 2022, with distribution conducted via hyperlinks. Subsequently, the collected responses underwent a comprehensive descriptive statistical analysis, in accordance with ACF principles, to derive meaningful insights and trends. The target demographic for questionnaire distribution encompassed representatives from both the public and private sectors within Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. In the public sector domain, we reached out to individuals occupying decision-making roles within national, regional, and local governmental entities. In parallel, within the private sector, we engaged a diverse array of industry and business stakeholders, including entrepreneurs, cluster coordinators, association members, farmer/forester unions, land managers, and others. This outreach extended primarily, but not exclusively, to professionals within sectors such as agriculture, forestry, food processing, energy, wood processing, paper production, chemicals, tourism and hospitality, environmental management and protection, as well as rural and urban development. By encompassing this broad spectrum of stakeholders, our questionnaire sought to comprehensively capture the multifaceted landscape of bioeconomy perceptions and sentiments across the Mekong region.

These target groups were chosen in accordance with the Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF) (Sabatier, 1988). The ACF focuses on the interactions among different policy actors, their beliefs, and their influence on the policy outcomes. In a comparative perspective, the ACF

can be used to analyse how different advocacy coalitions interact and compete in shaping the perception of the bioeconomy concept across multiple states or regions.

The Chiang Mai University (Thailand), Vietnam National University (Vietnam), and Savannakhet University (Laos) co-authors distributed the questionnaire via email, which contained the detailed purpose of the data collection and a link to the questionnaire in the local language. During the handling of the results of the questionnaires, the participants of the questionnaire were informed about the purpose and the principles of data protection, in analogy to the EU GDPR Regulation. The data were collected anonymously (i.e., it was not possible to directly assign the answer to a specific respondent) between December 19, 2022 and February 12, 2023. During this time, two reminder messages were sent to the respondents to fill out the questionnaires. We received 106 responses in total (Thailand - 51, Vietnam - 33, Laos - 22).

3. Results

3.1. Document analysis

The qualitative document analysis resulted in a list of documents that were further divided into two groups presented in Table 1, Table 2, and Appendix 1. The first table contains summary information on the official documents and strategies at the national levels. These documents are sorted by the country, year of publication and corresponding keyword (see Appendix 1 for details). The “other” in the “keywords” category includes keywords such as agriculture, renewable energy, resources, environment, emissions, cleaner production, biodiversity, and biotechnology. Five relevant documents were identified in Thailand, 13 in Vietnam, and 11 in Laos, i.e., 29 documents were found to relate to the bioeconomy in total. Document issuing bodies were governments, ministries, and other government or administration institutions, though, in several cases, international organisations were found to have issued the relevant documents. Aside from the official documents, we reviewed the presence of the bioeconomy in research and industry-related documents. In total, 26 scientific and other articles, books, and book chapters related to the bioeconomy were found and are reported in Table 2. Interestingly, no scientific publications mentioned or were related to the bioeconomy in Laos. In Thailand, ten documents were found, of which the majority were research and review articles published during the last three years and 16 documents were found in Vietnam. The majority of the documents were research articles (14), of which, six were written in Vietnamese.

3.2. Questionnaire

Within the General questions group (9 questions), the respondents answered identification questions, the aim of which was to obtain information about the profile and structure of the respondents from the point of view of their affiliation to the sector, type of industry, job position, relationship to the employer, gender, age, and type of education achieved. The Bioeconomy part (13 questions) contained general questions about whether the respondents had ever encountered the terms sustainable development, sustainable forest management, circular economy, bioeconomy, and, at the same time, expressed, using the six-point Likert scale method, what they imagined under some of these terms. In some questions, they also expressed their perception of the role

Table 1
Official documents and strategies reporting on the bioeconomy topic.

Country	Number of documents	Years of publication
Thailand	5	2018–2022
Vietnam	13	2004–2022
Laos	11	2005–2022

Source: own processing.

Table 2

Other outputs connected to the bioeconomy (articles, books, book chapters, official reports).

Country	Number of documents	Years of publication
Thailand	10	2021–2022
Vietnam	16	2001–2022
Laos	0	N/A

Source: own processing.

of the state in the bioeconomy and the barriers to this concept. The third part (the Forest Bioeconomy Part) contained a total of 4 questions regarding the focus of the forestry sector and forest bioeconomy in the surveyed states. The respondents could add their own opinions to several answers. The description of the participants from the three countries can be seen in [Table 3](#).

3.3. Bioeconomy and forest bioeconomy

Considering the connection between the bioeconomy and other concepts, the majority of the respondents perceived they understood the term “sustainable development”. Interestingly, one-third of the Vietnamese respondents answered they only partially knew what the term stands for. A smaller share, 14%, of Thai respondents stated that they partly understood it (and a further 4% said they never heard it). In contrast, almost all the Lao respondents stated they had full understanding of what sustainable development means. The respondents viewed sustainable forest management as the key for the long-term use of forest resources and agreed that the concept was implemented in the management of forests in the countries.

The circular economy, another concept compatible with the bioeconomy, was not as well-known to the respondents, as sustainable development. Overall, more than 61% of the respondents stated that they knew the term and what it meant, though the majority of the Vietnamese respondents, for example, stated they either had no or partial knowledge of the term and its meaning (55%). In Thailand and Laos, the term was better known, with about 70% of the respondents claiming complete knowledge of its meaning. The majority of the respondents also viewed the circular economy as a vital component of sustainable development and saw it as compatible with concepts aimed at mitigating and adapting to climate change.

As it turned out, the bioeconomy was the least known concept of the three – 38% of the respondents knew the term and its contents completely, while 44% claimed partial knowledge and 18% claimed they did not recognise it. Indeed, only in Thailand, the majority of the participants claimed they understood the term (51%), while in Laos, it was 41%, and in Vietnam it was 15%. However, a substantial share of both the Vietnamese and Lao participants claimed partial knowledge of the term and its meaning (73 and 50%, respectively). A substantial part of the respondents ([Fig. 1](#)) strongly believed that the bioeconomy is aimed at changing the production and consumption patterns towards more sustainable products and it is the aim to sustainably manage natural resources (mean score of 5.2), and to achieve global sustainable

development (mean score of 5.06). The perceptions of the first two highest-scoring perceived aims did not vary substantially between the participants based on their countries, however, belief that the bioeconomy is aimed at achieving sustainable development was more than 10% (0.64 points) or 7.5% (0.46 points) stronger in Vietnam or Laos (respectively) than in Thailand. The respondents least associated the improvement of public health with bioeconomy goals, though the mean score was quite high (4.81) with a small variability in the scores between the countries.

Looking specifically at the forest bioeconomy, the respondents associated it with mitigating the impacts of climate change (5.04), followed by the emergence of new technologies in the forest-based industries (5.03), or the use of forest-based residue (4.98). However, the differences between the scoring in individual items were relatively small, the mean scores ranged from 4.43 (non-production ecosystem services) to the aforementioned 5.04 for climate change mitigation. Although the associations between the forest bioeconomy coverage and the particular listed items were stronger in Vietnam than in Thailand, the variability of the mean scores was very similar – in Vietnam, the combined mean score was 5.36 with a difference between the lowest and highest mean item scores at 0.66 points, whereas in Thailand, the combined mean score was 4.58 with a 0.74 point difference. In Laos, on the other hand, the difference between the lowest and highest scored items was almost double than that observed in Vietnam (mean combined score 4.70, difference 1.27 points).

The majority of the respondents believed the bioeconomy was already covered by policy documents in their respective countries, either fully or partially (34 and 13% respectively), though a similar share stated they did not know whether this was the case (45%). Those who provided specific answers stated various sectoral policies and strategies spanning from forests, through agriculture, the environment to cross-sectoral documents, such as the Thai Bio-Circular-Green model or the Lao sustainable development policy.

Based on the responses, half of the questionnaire participants ([Fig. 2](#)) believed that the governments in the region provided some form of support to facilitate the transition to a bioeconomy, and only 6% stated that there was no government support for the transition. However, a considerable share (45%) responded that they did not know whether the governments provided any support for the bioeconomy transition. Of those who answered they had some level of knowledge, 25% thought that the support was from a national level government, followed by comprehensive support on all government levels, and about 8% of the respondents perceived that regional or municipal governments provided some form of support for the bioeconomy transition (approximately 4% in each country). The respondents believed strongly (mean score of 5.10) that the governments facilitated knowledge transfer, provided information support (5.10), supported the uptake of voluntary actions of companies (4.93), and provided investment support (4.93). The ranking of the particular items in the questions was rather uniform across the countries, though interestingly, the Lao respondents also believed that their government supported the transition by preparing strategic documents (5.00).

Considering the barriers to the uptake of the bioeconomy ([Fig. 3](#)), the

Table 3

Description of the sample as gathered through the questionnaire in Thailand, Vietnam and Laos.

Country	No. ^a	Gender ratio (F/M/O ^b ; %)	Education field ^c (%)	Age interval (y)	Industry ^c (%)	Relationship with the employer ^d (%)	Job level ^c (%)
Thailand	51	51/49/0	Environmental management (25); Science (22); Economics (16)	31–45	More than one (39); Agriculture (14); Forestry (12)	Employee (74)	Staff (49); Managerial (10); Executive (8)
Vietnam	33	55/45/0	Environmental management (61); Forestry (12); Agriculture (9)	18–30	Environment (39); Forestry (15); Agriculture (9)	Employee (93)	Staff (48); Managerial (9); Executive (3)
Laos	22	55/45/0	Forestry (50); Environmental management (32); Education (9)	31–45	Forestry (36); Education (23); Environment (18)	Employee (86)	Staff (50); Managerial (18); Executive (9)

^a Number of respondents; ^bGender ratio Female/Male/Other; ^cthree most frequent answers; ^dmost frequent answer.

Fig. 1. Perception of the bioeconomy aims. The vertices show options, the lines present scores on a six-point Likert scale. ^asustainable natural resource management; ^bclimate change adaptation and mitigation; ^cachieving sustainable development; ^dimproving public health; ^eremoving the dependence on fossil fuels; ^fchanging production/consumption patterns, ^gbalancing social development.

Fig. 2. Stacked bar chart showing the support for the bioeconomy transition by the governments in Thailand, Laos and Vietnam based on the six-point Likert scale.

aggregated results showed that the respondents rated all the listed potential barriers as similarly valid. The combined mean score for all the items was 4.75, ranging from 4.36 (low awareness of the stakeholders) to 4.86 (unclear strategic vision for the bioeconomy). The Thai respondents, though, provided answers with more variability, with the lowest score of 4.15 for the low awareness of the stakeholders and the highest score of 5.12 for insufficient financial incentives for the bioeconomy uptake. In Vietnam and Laos, the respondents rated the particular items as similarly relevant, with the item mean scores not exceeding 0.25 points from the combined means in the countries.

Regarding the industries that are related to the bioeconomy in the particular countries, the variability in the responses was larger than for

the previous questions. The association between the bioeconomy and the industries was smaller overall for all the listed items, ranging from 3.53 in the case of the construction industry to 4.85 in the case of agriculture. Relatively strong associations were also found for forestry (mean score of 4.75) and food processing (4.73). Interestingly, in Laos, the association between biotechnology and the bioeconomy was strong (mean score 5.04), whereas, in Thailand and Vietnam, the association was substantially weaker (by 17.6 and 14%, respectively).

Looking at the use of forest resources, the respondents mostly thought that they were not being used to their full potential (56%) and a further 16% thought that the resources were indeed used insufficiently. Only about 8% of the respondents thought that the forest resources were

Fig. 3. Stacked bar chart showing the barriers hindering the bioeconomy (BE) in Thailand, Laos and Vietnam based on the six-point Likert scale.

being used completely, without any room for increasing their use, and 20% had no knowledge about their use. Naturally, the respondents associated dendromass and phytomass with forest resources the strongest (mean scores 4.7 and 4.9, respectively), while forest fruits or bark had weaker association (approximate score of 4.3 each). Country-wise, the Vietnamese expressed a stronger relationship of the particular listed items to forest resources, while the Thais expressed a lower relationship, and the Lao rated it somewhere in between the two other countries.

Our next question aimed at identifying the perceived transformation of bioresources into products (Fig. 4). Unsurprisingly, established products, with a long tradition of using forest resources, such as food stuffs (4.86), furniture (4.78), or packaging (4.56) scored higher than novel products, such as electronic components (3.72) or bio-plastics

(4.09). In the more industrialised Thailand and Vietnam, the associations between the resources and the related products was stronger overall than in Laos, where the mean scores for the non-traditional products were lower than in the other countries. For example, bio-composites scored 3.50 in Laos, whereas, in Thailand and Vietnam, they scored 4.69 and 4.57, respectively.

4. Discussion

In countries of the global north, there is a clear real development of bioeconomy supported by the adopted strategies (Dietz et al., 2018; Thrän and Moesenfechtel, 2020; Lühhmann, 2020), conducted research (Holmgren et al., 2020; Dabbert et al., 2017) and, at the same time, a wider perception on the part of various interested parties (Backhouse

Fig. 4. Perception of forest bioresources. The vertices show the question options, the lines show the scores on the six-point Likert scale.

et al., 2021; Banerjee et al., 2018; Dieken et al., 2021). From the study of Neill et al. (2023), the fundamental difference between the global south and the global north is also evident from the use of the terms related to the bioeconomy on social networks, i.e., dynamic communication channels of the lay and professional public.

Our research, guided by the Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF) concepts, sought to address the divergent perceptions surrounding the bioeconomy, particularly in the context of the forest-based bioeconomy. The proliferation of research activities closely related to the forest-based bioeconomy has highlighted a perceptual gap between innovations in the field and the traditional forest-based industry, as elucidated by Ranacher et al. (2020).

It should be noted that there is a big potential of educational institutions towards influencing the bioeconomy perceptions by explaining, communicating, and transferring the knowledge and findings related to bioeconomy into practice. Usually, higher educational institutions proactively act to close the gaps in understanding and perceptions, especially when it comes to new and topical areas, including the bioeconomy. Then, to supplement our own observations, we reviewed the Web of Science (WoS) database for relevant publications, regionally focused on Thailand, Laos, and Vietnam. Indeed, this step serves to provide a broader context for understanding how regional higher education and research institutions, who author a major part of scientific publications, understand bioeconomy and what areas it encompasses.

Utilizing the ACF lens, we employed WoS to categorize research outcomes according to their originating countries. As of March 14th, 2023, our database search revealed 70 documents (after cross-comparison and overlapping check), while interestingly, these documents were published only recently (in or after the year 2017), which is unlike the situation in other regions, e.g., in Europe.

Alas, in the realm of forest bioeconomy, a mere seven outputs were unearthed, with five attributed to Vietnam and three to Thailand, with one document being jointly listed for both nations. This observation underscores the nascent nature of the bioeconomy concept within these countries, a finding also extending to the forest-based bioeconomy. In stark contrast, the WoS database unveiled a striking 7295 results pertaining to the broader bioeconomy, with Germany claiming the lion's share at 1325 publications. Similarly, there were 1129 results associated with the forest bioeconomy, with Finland leading the pack at 377 publications. These figures underscore the more established status of the bioeconomy, particularly the forest-based variant, in countries such as Germany and Finland compared to the emerging nature of these concepts in Southeast Asian nations like Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos.

The article tried to provide a comparative perspective on the bioeconomy perception through the ACF (advocacy coalition framework) lenses. Within the context of the bioeconomy, advocacy coalitions could consist of stakeholders from industries, academia, environmental organisations, government agencies, and other relevant actors. With the help of the online questionnaire, we tried to reach the relevant groups of stakeholders identified with ACF. The research presented has several limitations, especially regarding the response rate to the questionnaires and the resulting composition of the selected sample. The sample contained answers predominantly from representatives with higher education, so it is not possible to generalise the conclusion to the whole populations of the researched states. Furthermore, a certain influence was likely to be caused by the way these persons were selected by the participating universities. To enable the generalisation to whole populations, further research is needed that would target other stakeholder groups (e.g., local community members or industrial actors) and participants with a wider variability of education levels or occupations.

The low numbers of respondents introduced some risks connected to the drawn conclusions. For the conclusion described to be more substantial, it would be appropriate to confirm it using controlled interviews, similar to Lovrić et al. (2021). However, for the initial analysis of the perception and development of bioeconomy in the surveyed

states, the chosen procedure was considered as sufficient, even with the low numbers of respondents associated with our conclusions – i.e., i) low awareness of the bioeconomy, and ii) insufficient promotion of the concept from the state level.

In the past, a comparison study that included stakeholders in Thailand, was performed by Johnson et al. (2022), but was not specifically comparing Asian countries (authors focused on Thailand, Sweden, Rwanda and Colombia). Their findings also revealed that Thailand is very important for bioeconomy development in ASEAN countries. More research was devoted to the perception of the bioeconomy among citizens of different countries (Sleenhoff et al., 2015; Macht et al., 2022; Hempel et al., 2019). One actor group important for the future of the bioeconomy are students. A survey on the bioeconomy perception among students in 29 universities across Europe was performed in 2020, informing about the growing demand for a bioeconomy education and, at the same time, stating forestry as being the most important bioeconomy industry. Seventy percent of the respondents also confirmed that they already heard about the bioeconomy (Masiero et al., 2020). A similar study oriented on bioeconomy perceptions among students was performed in Slovakia (Výboštok et al., 2022). However, we do not know of any research that deals with the perception of the bioeconomy in the researched Asian countries. All the scientific outputs we tracked deal with European countries – e.g., Austria (Stern et al., 2018), Finland (Vainio et al., 2019), the Netherlands (Sleenhoff et al., 2015), Slovakia (Navrátilová et al., 2021), and Germany (Dallendörfer et al., 2022). The common denominator is the complexity of a precise definition, or the ambiguity of the bioeconomy terminology, accompanied by a connection to the concept of sustainable development and nature protection. This conclusion is also confirmed by our study. A certain difference in our conclusions compared to the study of Macht et al. (2022) can be seen in the depth of the understanding of the bioeconomy concept. Macht et al. (2022) stated that a strong emphasis on the necessity of technological progress and development will contribute to the bioeconomy, whereas, in the surveyed states of the Mekong region, the perceptions focused more on the bioeconomy's biological component (up to the basal). This means that the respondents associated the bioeconomy with the protection of bioresources and their efficient use.

To contextualise the concept of the bioeconomy in the Mekong region, a bioeconomy- (and forest bioeconomy-) focused workshop was organised in Bangkok, in November 2022 between representatives of Kasetsart University, Chiang Mai University, Souphanouvong University, and Savannakhet University. This is in line with the view of Mukhtarov et al. (2017) in which the bioeconomy is mostly discussed by the “golden triangle” of the government, universities, and industry. The participants of the workshop (a total of 18 people, approximately equally divided between Thailand and Laos) were first asked to fill in the same questionnaire that was sent out as part of our research. Subsequently, representatives of the Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences of the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague presented a series of interactive lectures on the concept of the bioeconomy and forest bioeconomy. In the last phase, the different approaches of Laos and Thailand were discussed from the point of view of representatives of the academic sphere. The Thai representatives connected the bioeconomy to sustainability, economic growth, carbon neutrality, job creation, and the use of renewable bioresources. The Lao representatives mentioned only the latter two plus a green economy. Financial support and investment in human resources were highlighted as the most important conditions for a successful bioeconomy transition in both countries. The other mentioned items were, e.g., the need of high-tech infrastructure, policy incentives, and digital technologies. In further research, it would be possible to include representatives of other groups (e.g., the media) among the respondents, similarly to Dieken et al. (2021) or introduce the research in more Mekong region countries. One of the current initiatives, the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) Initiative on Governing Bioeconomy Pathways, aims to facilitate a more cohesive and constructive dialogue among stakeholders (SEI, 2023).

5. Conclusions

The study we are presenting here was undertaken with the goal of comprehending the perceptions of the bioeconomy among stakeholders in the Mekong region, specifically in surveyed states: Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. To achieve this, we employed various methodological approaches, drawing inspiration from the Advocacy Coalition Framework (ACF), to assess the practical implementation of the bioeconomy within the national economies of these countries. Additionally, we sought to probe the depth of understanding of the bioeconomy concept among the stakeholders, identify commonalities, distinctions, and nuances between these nations, and not least, shed light on the factors that support or hinder the further development of the bioeconomy. The outcomes of our extensive analyses are presented herein, offering comprehensive responses to the research inquiries guided by the ACF principles: (i) Perception and Application of the Bioeconomy: Through the lens of the ACF, we delved into the stakeholders' perceptions and the practical integration of the bioeconomy within the national economic frameworks of Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. (ii) Understanding the Bioeconomy Concept: Utilizing ACF concepts, we examined the depth of comprehension of the bioeconomy concept among stakeholders in the surveyed states of the Mekong region. (iii) Comparing National Approaches: Drawing from ACF's analytical framework, we identified both commonalities and unique distinctions in how these nations approach and implement the bioeconomy. (iv) Supporting Factors and Barriers: The ACF informed our exploration of the various factors, both supportive and inhibitory, that influenced the trajectory of bioeconomy development in these countries.

The result of our analyses are presented as answers to the research questions:

RA1: Dedicated bioeconomy strategies in Thailand, Vietnam and Laos did not exist at the time of conducting the study. The bioeconomy is closely connected to the circular economy and sustainable development. Official documents, that can be connected to bioeconomy, were issued mostly by governmental and ministerial bodies, but none of them explicitly mentioned the term "bioeconomy". The closest connection could be seen in the BCG model adopted by Thailand in 2021. Despite the fact that it was possible to perceive various efforts from the government level to adopt the concept of a bioeconomy (e.g., in the case of Vietnam), the transition to a bioeconomy was still in the initial phase.

RA2: From our questionnaire, it is possible to conclude that a significant part of the respondents perceived the bioeconomy as a concept that focuses on the production and consumption of sustainable products, an effort to sustainably use natural resources and as a way to achieve sustainable development. The connection between the bioeconomy and sustainable development was, therefore, obvious from the perspective of the countries we focused on.

RA3: The evaluated stakeholders deemed an unclear bioeconomy vision, the insufficient support from the state administration, and the low technological development as crucial barriers to the bioeconomy transition. Clear communication pathways between high-level state administration and other stakeholders is, therefore, an essential tool in the bioeconomy deployment in the researched countries.

RA4: The questionnaire responses showed that, in the more technologically developed Thailand and Vietnam, it is possible to look for a focus not only on traditional bioeconomy outputs, but also on more technologically demanding production, while in Laos, the technological development must precede the development in this direction. The first steps in the development of the bioeconomy should therefore be directed in the traditional way, i.e., towards the sustainable use of natural resources in each country (including wood and non-wood forest products).

The responses showed a clear connection between forestry and the bioeconomy concept in all the researched countries. Even if results showed that the focus was on different forest products and services in each country, this sector was perceived as having an irreplaceable role in the bioeconomy.

Further research can be focused, for example, on the economic valuation of the bioeconomy (or forest bioeconomy) in national economies, e.g., the contribution of the bioeconomy to the GDP, its value added, and job creation. These indicators can be monitored in the individual countries and evaluated. Key policymakers in the individual countries must take on the key role they play in the greater involvement of bioeconomy principles in economic activities. Without their support, further development will be very difficult. The other further research suggestions are also to enlarge the study focus on more countries of the Mekong region or to compare the bioeconomy in the Mekong region with the situation in selected European countries.

Funding

This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport of the Czech Republic (Grant number CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000803), by Erasmus+ Key Action 2 (number 618803-EPP-1-2020-1-FI-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP) and by Horizon Europe (Grant number 101071314).

Compliance with ethical standards

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author statement

Authors acknowledge that the material presented in this manuscript has not been previously published, except in abstract form, nor is it simultaneously under consideration by any other journal.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Radek Rinn: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Jankovský:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Petra Palátová:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Sandra Paola García-Jácome:** Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Alice Sharp:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Prasit Wangpakattanonwong:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Nataša Lovrić:** Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Manh Vu Van:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Minh Doan Thi Nhat:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Bounheuang Ninchaleune:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Inta Chanthavong:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Kongchan Doungmala:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data upon which this paper is based are available from the authors upon request.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful for the support provided by the project of excellent research EVA4.0 (*Advanced research supporting the forestry and*

wood processing sectors' adaptation to global change and the 4th industrial revolution, CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000803) granted by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport of the Czech Republic, by FRAME (*Forests, climate change mitigation and adaptation: Higher Education Cooperation in Mekong region*) granted by Erasmus+ Key Action 2: Capacity Building in the field of Higher Education and by the project

BETTER Life (*Bringing Excellence to Transformative Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences through Integrated Digital Centers*), granted by Horizon Europe.

The authors also wish to thank all the participants of the questionnaire survey.

Appendix A. Appendix 1: Document analysis

Official documents and strategies			
Country	Year of issue	Issued by	Key = word
Thailand			
BCG Model: Fostering Sustainable Development in Thai Economy	2021	Thai Government	bioeconomy
BIO-CIRCULAR-GREEN ECONOMY 2021–2027 ACTION PLAN (+draft)	2022 (2021)	Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation	bioeconomy
Evolutionary Acts and Global Economic Transition: Progress of the Circular Economy in ASEAN	2018	Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia	circular economy
Circular economy: Shaping a sustainable future	2019	Thailand Board of Investment	circular economy
THAILAND'S BIO-CIRCULAR-GREEN ECONOMY Living up to Global Challenges	2021	Thailand Board of Investment	bioeconomy
Vietnam	Year of issue	Issued by	Keyword
Resolution No. 24-NQ/TW: Proactive response to climate change, improvement of natural resource management and environmental protection	2004	Communist Party of Vietnam	other
Resolution No. 41-NQ/TW: Environmental protection in the period of industrialization and modernization	2004	Communist Party of Vietnam	other
Decision No. 1419/QĐ-TTg: Approval of the strategy on cleaner production in industry to 2020	2009	Government of Vietnam	other
Decision No. 432/QĐ-TTg: Approval of sustainable development strategy of Vietnam period 2011–2020	2012	Government of Vietnam	sustainability
Decision No. 1393/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister: Approving the National Strategy on Green Growth	2015	The Prime Minister	green economy
Circular No. 128/2016/TT-BTC: On export duty exemption and reduction for environment-friendly products and products from recycling and waste treatment prescribed in the Government's Decree No. 19/2015/ND-CP of February 14, 2015, detailing a number of articles of the law on environmental protection (dated 9 August 2016), Hanoi.	2016	Government of Vietnam	other
Decision 452/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister approving the project on promoting the handling and use of ash, slag and gypsum of thermal power, chemical and fertilizer plants as secondary material source for construction materials and in construction works	2017	Government of Vietnam	other
Decree 102/2020/ND-CP stipulating the legal timber assurance system in Vietnam	2020	Government of Vietnam	forestry
Decision No. 523/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister: Approving the Vietnam forestry development strategy for the period of 2021–2030, with a vision to 2050	2021	Government of Vietnam	forestry
Decision No. 687/QĐ-TTg of the Prime Minister: Approving the Scheme for Economy Development in Vietnam	2022	Government of Vietnam	other
Resolution No. 36-NQ/TW: Development and application of biotechnology to serve the country's sustainable development in the new situation	2023	Government of Vietnam	other
An overview of the use of plants and animals in traditional medicine systems in Viet Nam	2008	TRAFFIC Southeast Asia	other
Vietnam Forestry Development Strategy: Implementation results for 2006–2020 and recommendations for the 2021–2030 strategy	2020	Center for International Forestry Research (CIFOR)	forestry
Laos	Year of issue	Issued by	Keyword
Forestry strategy to the year 2025 of the Lao PDR	2005	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	forestry
Agriculture Development Strategy to 2025 and Vision to the year 2030	2015	Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	other
Vision Year 2030 Strategy Year 2025 of Environment Protection Fund	2018	Environment Protection Fund	other
National Green Growth Strategy of the Lao PDR till 2030	2018	(Secretariat for Formulation of National Green Growth Strategy of the Lao PDR	green economy
Lao People's Democratic Republic: Voluntary National Review on the Implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development	2018	Government of the Lao People's Democratic Republic in consultation with National and International Partners in Lao PDR	sustainability
Forestry Law	2019	National Assembly	forestry
The 9th five-year national socio-economic development plan (2021–2025)	2020	Ministry of Planning and investment	other
Lao PDR Green Climate Fund Country Programme 2021–2023	2021	Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment	other
National Strategy on Climate Change of the Lao PDR: Vision to the year 2050, Strategy and Programs of Actions to the year 2030 (draft)	2021	Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment	other
Decarbonization in Lao PDR: the options and challenges	2021	ASEAN Green Future report,	other
Energy Transition Pathways for the 2030 Agenda SDG 7 Roadmap for the Lao People's Democratic Republic	2022	United Nations	sustainability

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Laos	Year of issue	Issued by	Keyword	
Thailand				
Agricultural and Municipal Waste Management in Thailand	2020	circular economy	Fukuda, S. (2021). Agricultural and Municipal Waste Management in Thailand. In: Liu, L., Ramakrishna, S. (eds) An Introduction to Circular Economy. Springer, Singapore. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-8510-4_16	book chapter
Recent Situation and Progress in Biorefining Process of Lignocellulosic Biomass: Towards Green Economy	2020	development	Cheng, Y. S., Mutrakulcharoen, P., Chuetor, S., Cheenkachorn, K., Tantayotai, P., Panakkal, E. J., & Sriariyanun, M. (2020). Recent situation and progress in biorefining process of lignocellulosic biomass: Towards green economy. Applied Science and Engineering Progress, 13(4), 299–311.	article (review)
The circular economy practices of the Tapioca Starch Industry in Northeastern Thailand	2021	circular economy	Charoenrungrueang, C., Sawettham, A., Ngeoywijit, S., Weesaphen, S., & Kosacka-Olejnik, M. (2021). The circular economy practices of the Tapioca Starch Industry in Northeastern Thailand. Zeszyty Naukowe Politechniki Poznańskiej. Organizacja i Zarządzanie.	article
Small forest growers in tropical landscapes should be embraced as partners for Green-growth: Increase wood supply, restore land, reduce poverty, and mitigate climate change	2021	forestry	Nambiar, E. S. (2021). Small forest growers in tropical landscapes should be embraced as partners for Green-growth: Increase wood supply, restore land, reduce poverty, and mitigate climate change. Trees, Forests and People, 6, 100,154.	article
Urban Agriculture and BCG Economic Model	2021	other	Chaima, R., Norsuwan, T., Utthasuk, K., Punyasai, T., Saltikulnukarn, T., Suppakittpaisarn, P., Yaipimol, E., Surinseng, V., Charoenlerthanakit, N., & Kaeomuangmoon, T. (2021). Urban Agriculture and BCG Economic Model. Journal of Agricultural Research and Extension, 38(3), 100–116.	article (review)
BCG (Bio-Circular-Green) economy in Thailand	2022	bioeconomy	Kumaga, S. (2022). BCG (Bio-Circular-Green) economy in Thailand. RIM Pacific Business and Industries Vol XXII No. 84 2–31.	report
Thailand's BCG Transformation: 40 Case Studies on the Bio-Circular-Green Strategy and the Sufficiency Economy Philosophy in Action	2022	bioeconomy	NIDA's Sustainable Development and Sufficiency Economy Studies Center. 2022. Thailand's BCG Transformation: 40 Case Studies on the Bio-Circular-Green Strategy and the Sufficiency Economy Philosophy in Action. Sirivatana Interprint.	book
Sustainability factors influencing para rubber resources for the implementation of circular economy in Songkhla province, southern Thailand	2022	sustainability	John Nyandansobi Simon, Kingsley Okpara, Narissara Nuthammachot & Kuaanan Techato (2022) Sustainability factors influencing para rubber resources for the implementation of circular economy in Songkhla province, southern Thailand, International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2022.2124551	article
Environmental Sustainability of Waste Circulation Models for Sugarcane Biorefinery System in Thailand	2022	sustainability	Silalertruksa T, Wirodcharuskul C, Gheewala SH. Environmental Sustainability of Waste Circulation Models for Sugarcane Biorefinery System in Thailand. Energies. 2022; 15(24):9515.DOI: https://doi.org/10.3390/en15249515	article
Transition Pathway Palm Oil Research Framework Towards a Bio-Circular-Green Economy Model Using SWOT Analysis: A Case Study of Thailand	2022	sustainability	Usapein, P., Tuntiwattanapun, N., Polburee, P., Veerakul, P., Seekao, C., & Chavalparit, O. (2022). Transition Pathway Palm Oil Research Framework Towards a Bio-Circular-Green Economy Model Using SWOT Analysis: A Case Study of Thailand. Frontiers in Environmental Science, 825.	article
Vietnam				
A survey of medicinal plants in BaVi National Park, Vietnam: methodology and implications for conservation and sustainable use	2001	sustainability	Tran Van, On & do, Quyen & Bich, Le & Jones, Bill & Wunder, Josette & Russell-Smith, Jeremy. (2001). A survey of medicinal plants in BaVi National Park, Vietnam: Methodology and implications for conservation and sustainable use. Biological Conservation. 97. 295–304. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(00)00125-7 .	article
The changing administration and role of forestry in the economy of Vietnam	2004	forestry	Hieu, P.S. The changing administration and role of forestry in the economy of Vietnam. Small-scale Forestry 3, 85–98 (2004). DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/s11842-004-0006-1	article
Economic and environmental efficiency of biogas plant in livestock waste treatment in O Sa vermicelli village, Thua Thien Hue province Hiệu quả kinh tế và môi trường của công trình khí sinh học trong xử lý chất thải chăn nuôi tại làng bún Ô Sa, tỉnh Thừa Thiên Huế	2015	other	Tran Anh Tuan, Pham Thi My Hanh. Department of Environmental Science, Hue University of Sciences. Available at: https://repository.vnu.edu.vn/	article (Vietnamese)
Analyzing the transformations of forest PES in Vietnam: Implications for REDD +	2016	forestry	Traedal, Leif & Vedeld, Pål & Petursson, Jon. (2015). Analyzing the transformations of forest PES in Vietnam: Implications for REDD+. Forest Policy and Economics. 62. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2015.11.001 .	article
Circular Economy in Vietnam	2019	circular economy	Hai, H.T., Quang, N.D., Thang, N.T., Nam, N.H. (2020). Circular Economy in Vietnam. In: Ghosh, S. (eds) Circular Economy: Global Perspective. Springer, Singapore. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1052-6_22	book chapter
Implementing Circular Economy: International Experience and Policy Implications for Vietnam Thực hiện kinh tế tuần hoàn: Kinh nghiệm quốc tế và gợi ý chính sách cho Việt Nam	2019	circular economy	Nam, N., & Hanh, N. (2019). Implementing Circular Economy: International Experience and Policy Implications for Vietnam. VNU JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, 35(4)	article (Vietnamese)

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Implementation of biogas digester to clean up pig livestock and provide community with biogas renewable energy (CBRE)	2020	other	Tran, Nam & Thao, Huynh & Cong Khanh, Huynh & Diem, Huynh & Dinh, Danh. (2021). Xây dựng mô hình biogas xử lý chất thải chăn nuôi heo và cung cấp năng lượng tái tạo khí sinh học cho cộng đồng. Dong Thap University Journal of Science. 10. 64–76. DOI: 10.52714/dthu.10.3.2021.869 .	article (Vietnamese)
Xây dựng mô hình biogas xử lý chất thải chăn nuôi heo và cung cấp năng lượng tái tạo khí sinh học cho cộng đồng Economic Performance of Forest Plantations in Vietnam: Eucalyptus, <i>Acacia mangium</i> , and <i>Manglietia conifera</i>	2020	forestry	Cuong, T.; Chinh, T.T.Q.; Zhang, Y.; Xie, Y. Economic Performance of Forest Plantations in Vietnam: Eucalyptus, <i>Acacia mangium</i> , and <i>Manglietia conifera</i> . Forests 2020, 11, 284. DOI: https://doi.org/10.3390/f11030284	article
Forest governance and economic values of forest ecosystem services in Vietnam	2020	forestry	Nguyen, Duc & Ancev, Tiho & Randall, Alan. (2020). Forest governance and economic values of forest ecosystem services in Vietnam. Land Use Policy. 97. 103,297. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2018.03.028 .	article
Vietnam's solar and wind power success: Policy implications for the other ASEAN countries	2021	other	Do, Thang & Burke, Paul & Hoang Nguyen, Nam & Overland, Indra & Suryadi, Beni & Swandaru, Akbar & Yurnaidi, Zulfikar. (2021). Vietnam's solar and wind power success: Policy implications for the other ASEAN countries. Energy for Sustainable Development. 56. 1–11.	article
Circular economic development in Vietnam	2021	circular economy	Dang Hoang Vu, Do The Son, Hoang Thi Thu Hoai, Vu Thi Cam Tu, Vu Thi Hanh Thu. Circular economic development in Vietnam Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol. 27, No. 52021DOI: 10.47750/cibg.2021.27.05.034	article
Circular economy - sustainable development direction for businesses Kinh tế tuần hoàn - hướng phát triển bền vững cho doanh nghiệp	2021	circular economy	Chau An. (Oct 2021). Circular economy - sustainable development direction for businesses. Portal of the Ministry of Industry and Trade. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from https://moit.gov.vn/phan-trien-ben-vung/kinh-te-tuan-hoan-thuc-day-cho-chien-luoc-san-xuat-va-ti-eu-dung-ben-vung.html	Article (Vietnamese)
Promoting circular economy to realize sustainable development goals Thúc đẩy kinh tế tuần hoàn để hiện thực hóa mục tiêu phát triển bền vững	2021	circular economy	The Hoang. (Oct 2021). Promoting circular economy to realize sustainable development goals. Journal of the Central Propaganda Department. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from https://tuyengiao.vn/kinh-te/thuc-day-kinh-te-tuan-hoan-de-hien-thuc-hoa-muc-tieu-phat-trien-ben-vung-136351	Article (Vietnamese)
Towards a biological circular economy: A brave and wise choice! Hướng tới nền kinh tế tuần hoàn sinh học: Sự lựa chọn dũng cảm và khôn ngoan!	2022	circular economy	Tong Minh. (July 2022). Towards a biological circular economy: A brave and wise choice! Newspaper of Natural Resources and Environment. Retrieved January 31, 2023, from https://baotainguyenmoitruong.vn/huong-toi-nen-kinh-te-tuan-hoan-sinh-hoc-su-lua-chon-dung-cam-va-khon-ngoaan-341429.html	Article (Vietnamese)
Measuring the Circular Economy for Companies: A Case Study of a Packaging Company in Vietnam	2022	circular economy	Khue, D., & Nam, N. (2022). Measuring the Circular Economy for Companies: A Case Study of a Packaging Company in Vietnam. VNU JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, 2(3). DOI: 10.57110/jeb.v2i3.4645	article (Vietnamese)
Adding Values to Agro-Industrial Byproducts for the Bioeconomy in Vietnam	2022	bioeconomy	Chu-Ky, Son & Thanh, Vu & Phi, Quyet-Tien & Anh, Tuan & To, Kim & Quan, Le-Ha & Nguyen, Tien-Thanh & Luong Hong, Nga & Trang, Vu Thu & Nguyen, Tien Cuong & Tuan Anh, Pham & Le, Ha & Quach, Ngoc Tung & Nguyen, Chinh-Nghia. (2022). Adding Values to Agro-Industrial Byproducts for the Bioeconomy in Vietnam. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003125679-5 .	book chapter

Appendix B. Appendix 2: Bioeconomy in Thailand, Vietnam and Laos – questionnaire

A.1. GENERAL QUESTIONS:

- 1) In which country do you operate:
 - a. Thailand
 - b. Laos
 - c. Vietnam
 - d. Internationally
 - e. Other (please specify):
- 2) What sector do you represent:
 - a. Government
 - b. Industry
 - c. Services
 - d. Non-profit sector
- 3) What sector of the economy do you represent:

A.1.1. Agriculture

- a. Forestry
- b. Wood working industry
- c. Paper industry

- d. More of the above-mentioned
- e. Other (please specify):

- 4) What job position do you hold:
- a. Owner
 - b. Management
 - c. Executive

A.1.2. *Administrative*

- d. Other (please specify)
- 5) What is your relationship with the employer:
- a. Employee
 - b. Self-employed
 - c. Maternity leave
 - d. Other (please specify):
- 6) Gender:
- a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Other
 - d. Do not want to say
- 7) What is your age:
- a. 18–30
 - b. 31–45
 - c. 46–60
 - d. 61 and over
- 8) What is your highest level of education:
- a. Primary education
 - b. Secondary education
 - c. Tertiary education
- 9) What field of study did you formally graduate from?

A.1.3. *Agriculture*

- a. Forestry
- b. Wood working
- c. Paper industry
- d. Other (please specify):

A.2. *BIOECONOMY PART:*

10) I have heard of the term sustainable development and I know what it means.

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Partly

11) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)
Sustainable forest management is:

key when considering long-term use of forest resources	1	2	3	4	5	6
implemented in my country and foresters take it into account when managing their forests	1	2	3	4	5	6

12) I have heard of the term circular economy and I know what it means.

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Partly

13) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)
A circular economy is:

a vital component of sustainable development	1	2	3	4	5	6
compatible with other economic concepts that aim at mitigating climate change effects and adapting to climate change	1	2	3	4	5	6

- 14) I have heard the term bioeconomy and I know what it means:
- Yes
 - No
 - Partly
- 15) What does bioeconomy mean to you? How do you understand the term bioeconomy?
Answer:
- 16) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)
The aim of the bioeconomy is:

the sustainable management of natural resources	1	2	3	4	5	6
the mitigation of climate change (adaptation and mitigation)	1	2	3	4	5	6
to achieve global sustainable development	1	2	3	4	5	6
to improve public health	1	2	3	4	5	6
to remove the dependence of fossil fuels	1	2	3	4	5	6
to change the production/consumption patterns globalisation towards more sustainable products	1	2	3	4	5	6
the integration and balancing of social development in rural and urban areas	1	2	3	4	5	6

- 17) Is the bioeconomy concept incorporated in a specific policy or strategic document in your country?
- Yes, in these:....
 - Partly, in which:....
 - No
 - I do not know
- 18) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)
In my country the bioeconomy is represented by:

Biotechnology	1	2	3	4	5	6
Energy	1	2	3	4	5	6
Agriculture	1	2	3	4	5	6
Forestry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Food	1	2	3	4	5	6
Chemistry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Construction	1	2	3	4	5	6
Wood working industry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Furniture industry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Paper industry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Tourism	1	2	3	4	5	6

Other:

- 19) Does the state authority give support to the bioeconomy transition and its practices uptake:
- Yes
 - No
 - I do not know
- 20) If the answer above is positive: The state support comes in the majority from:
- National level
 - Regional level
 - Local level
 - All levels
- 21) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)
If the state authority supports the bioeconomy transition, the support includes:

preparing strategic documents	1	2	3	4	5	6
providing direct financial subsidies	1	2	3	4	5	6
providing tax breaks	1	2	3	4	5	6
providing investment support	1	2	3	4	5	6
providing knowledge transfer	1	2	3	4	5	6
providing support services for subsidy schemes requests	1	2	3	4	5	6
supporting information support (e.g., info campaigns on environmentally friendly products, services, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5	6
supporting implementation of voluntary tools (e.g., ISO 14000, environmental management systems, environmental management and auditing systems etc.)	1	2	3	4	5	6

Other (please specify):

22) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)

The barriers which hinder bioeconomy in your country are:

Insufficient support from the state authority	1	2	3	4	5	6
Unclear strategic vision and needs for BE	1	2	3	4	5	6
Insufficient financial support for incentivising the uptake of BE	1	2	3	4	5	6
Low technological progress	1	2	3	4	5	6
Reluctance of the companies involved	1	2	3	4	5	6
low awareness among stakeholders	1	2	3	4	5	6

Other (please specify):

A.3. FOREST BIOECONOMY PART:

23) Renewable biological forest -based resources in your country are used:

- Completely (there is no room for increasing their use)
- Partly (there is room for increasing their use)
- Insufficiently
- I do not know

24) Do you agree with the statements below? (1 - least, 6 – most)

The forest-based renewable biological resources are:

Dendromass (forest biomass)	1	2	3	4	5	6
Bark	1	2	3	4	5	6
Logging residues	1	2	3	4	5	6
Phytomass	1	2	3	4	5	6
Forest berries	1	2	3	4	5	6
Forest mushrooms	1	2	3	4	5	6

Other (please specify):

25) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)

I believe that, in my country, other forest products (including wood) are used in the following:

Furniture industry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Biocomposites	1	2	3	4	5	6
Packaging materials	1	2	3	4	5	6
Biodegradable plastics	1	2	3	4	5	6
Bio-textiles	1	2	3	4	5	6
Food production	1	2	3	4	5	6
Pharmaceutical industry	1	2	3	4	5	6
Engineering	1	2	3	4	5	6
Energy production	1	2	3	4	5	6
Electronics industry	1	2	3	4	5	6

Other (please specify):

26) Do you agree with the opinion below? (1 - least, 6 – most)

The forest bioeconomy in my country covers these topics:

Wood (Dendromass) as a forest product	1	2	3	4	5	6
Non-productive (ecosystem) forest functions	1	2	3	4	5	6
Mitigation of climate change impacts	1	2	3	4	5	6
Utilisation of forest production waste	1	2	3	4	5	6
Research and education in forestry	1	2	3	4	5	6
New technologies (digitisation, ICT, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5	6
Sustainable development (semi-natural farming) with an emphasis on biodiversity	1	2	3	4	5	6
Economic aspects of forestry (rural development, creating functional value chains and supply networks, etc.)	1	2	3	4	5	6
Wood construction / wood-based products	1	2	3	4	5	6

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